

Proceedings of the Network Institute Academy Assistants program 2017/2018

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Preface

This volume contains the proceedings of the 2017/2018 edition of the Academy Assistant program organized by the Network Institute of Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (<http://networkinstitute.org/research/academy-assistants/>). With this program the Network Institute aims to interest bright young master students for conducting scientific research and pursuing an academic career. The program brings together scientists from different disciplines; every project combines methods & themes from informatics, social sciences and/or humanities. For each project, two student research assistants with different research backgrounds work together. The projects result in papers and/or research proposals. The program started in 2010 with 4 projects funded by the [KNAW](#).

For the 2017/2018 edition, six projects were selected to receive funding based on a review of submitted proposals by an independent committee. Each of these projects was then executed by two Academy Assistants during a 10-month period. The selected projects show a broad range of interdisciplinary research and a diverse range of topics.

Starting this year, in addition to papers and/or follow-up research proposals, the projects were asked to submit final papers describing the outcomes of the research projects. These papers are collected in these proceedings after having undergone a light reviewing process by the coordinators of the program. All papers are co-authored by the respective research assistants, the supervisors and other contributors. They reflect the broad spectrum of interdisciplinary work associated with the networked world.

We would like to thank the proposal review committee for assisting in the selection of the projects. We especially extend a special thank you to Marco Otte and Evert Haasdijk for their role in the Network Institute and this program.

We hope these proceedings will provide you with new inspirations for your research and opportunities for new and exiting collaborations.

Sincerely,

Victor de Boer, Antske Fokkens, Christine Moser and Ivar Vermeulen

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